

Employee Commitment and Culture Organization on Employee Performance

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze and examine the influence of employee commitment and cultural organizational factors towards employees of the Job Performance, Regional Secretariat (SetDa) Riau Province both simultaneously (overall test) and partial (individual test). The research method used is verification, while the population in this study is the Regional Secretariat (SetDa) Riau Province based on increasing totaling 402 people. By using the method of proportional stratified random sampling in the sample amount to obtain 40 respondents. While data collection technology is used by the field study and library that includes observation, interviews and questionnaires, and to determine the relationship and the influence of an independent variable to the model variables to use Multiple Linear Regression Analysis. The results showed that the calculated results obtained statistically Multiple Correlation Coefficient (R) was 0.8950 with $p < 0.05$ and the coefficient value of Determination (R²) 80.11%. This means that approximately 80.11% of employee commitment and organizational culture factors have a significant influence on employee job performance. Partial test showed that the partial coefficient of determination values contained in the organizational culture variables for $(r^2) = 54.58\%$ with $p = 0.00000$ and $t_{result} = 7.515 > t_{table} = 1.678$ and t_{table} variables for employee commitment $(r^2) = 78, 74\%$ with $p = 0.00000$ and $t_{result} = 13.196 > t_{table} = 1.678$. These results indicate that organizational cultural factors and employee commitment have a significant relationship influence on employee job performance of the Riau Province Regional Secretariat (SetDa).

INTRODUCTION

Within government agencies, it is known that there is a work culture of state officials. In accordance with the Decree of the Minister for Administrative Reform Number 25/KEP/M.PAN/04/2002 dated 25 April 2002, as a culture, the work culture of the state apparatus can be recognized in the form of the values contained therein, institutions or work systems, and attitudes. and the behavior of the HR apparatus that implements it. So the work culture of the state apparatus

In this decision, it is defined as the attitudes and behavior of individuals and groups of state officials that are based on values that are believed to be true and have become traits and habits in carrying out daily tasks and work. It is hoped that the work culture of state officials will be beneficial for both state officials and their work units, where they personally provide opportunities to play a role, achieve and self-actualize, while in groups can improve the quality of joint performance (Nurjanah, 2008: 21).

This employee commitment will create a cultural character in the organization so that it can improve performance and better work performance. On the basis of the above, in this research the author uses the employee commitment variable as a variable that influences (strengthens) the relationship and influence between organizational culture variables (independent variables) on performance variables (dependent variables). This means that if the level of employee commitment is high it will result in strengthening or emphasizing the relationship and influence between the new organizational culture variables and the level of employee performance, and vice versa. If changes occur in the internal and external aspects of the organization, the organizational culture will automatically tend to change.

So it is necessary to carry out an organizational culture audit, to ensure whether the organizational culture is still in line with and supports the new organization's internal affairs. The implementing party of the organization must be proactive about organizational change, if necessary, make planned or managed changes to adapt and increase consistency with the internal organization, then the change can achieve organizational goals towards effectiveness (Hodge et al., 2003: 470).

The Riau Provincial Government, especially the Regional Secretariat of Riau Province, requires commitment capabilities employees who will influence the behavior of carrying out tasks and the results achieved. For this reason, employees in carrying out their work will show an attitude that reflects what they feel, because attitude is basically the regularity of a person's feelings and thoughts and the tendency to act towards aspects of their environment. The attitudes related to work include the attitude of involvement work, job satisfaction and organizational commitment.

So if someone is involved in a job then he will be satisfied with that job and committed to the organization. Someone who is dissatisfied with work will be less involved in work and commitment to the organization will be low (Knoop, 2005: 645). The poor performance of employees within the Riau Province Regional Secretariat (Setda) is not solely caused by an inadequate number of employees, but according to the author's observations from research results (Nurjanah, 2008: 26) lies in the still low quality of employee performance, as in Kep. Menpan. 25/KEP/M.PAN/04/2002 describes several situations that occurred, including:

1. Lack of awareness of state officials to increase personal integrity and professionalism through improvements and capabilities in accordance with technology and actual conditions.
2. The leader still shows the attitude of a "feudal bureaucrat" who always demands that his subordinates be faithful and faithful, obey all orders and wishes, thereby developing an ABS (As long as you are happy) character in his subordinates.
3. Leaders do not have or lack the awareness to make their leadership qualities the center of positive attention and therefore be able to become role models for their subordinates.
4. There are no clear and firm sanctions if employees work inappropriately and not quickly.
5. The discipline and work regularity of the apparatus is still low, it is evident that many high-level officials are too busy attending coordination meetings in various places, and work late into the night, while many lower-level employees work only based on orders, so they are often unemployed if there are no orders from their superiors.
6. Work discipline and work regularity regulations have been outlined in complete work procedures but have not been implemented properly, are still formalities, and are far from being actualized in the form of concrete actions.
7. The dedication and loyalty of state officials is still low, there are even officials who make mistakes in applying loyalty only to their superiors, but are not loyal to the vision, mission and duties of their agency.

In this regard, it is necessary to carry out research to find out what factors What are the factors that influence employee performance?

Dwi Cahyono and Imam Ghozali (2002: 362) in their research stated that organizational culture has a positive effect on organizational commitment. Apart from that, Moon (2000: 192) in his research stated that intrinsic and extrinsic motivation and culture have a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. Meanwhile, Sulaiman (2002: 181) in his research stated that organizational commitment is positively related to employee performance. Based on the background above, the problems of this research are: 1) What is the description of the variables of employee commitment, organizational culture and employee achievement within the Regional Secretariat (Setda) of Riau Province; 2) Is there a significant influence between employee commitment and organizational culture factors simultaneously on the performance of Riau Province Regional Secretariat (Setda) employees; 3) Is there a significant influence between employee commitment factors partially on the performance of Riau Province Regional Secretariat (Setda) employees and 4) Is there a significant influence between partial organizational culture factors on the performance of Riau Province Regional Secretariat (Setda) employees.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Commitment

Commitment and culture cannot be separated from the most real impacts of the era of globalization is currently starting to be seen with increasing competition in all lines of organizations and institutions, both business organizations and government organizations and public service organizations, including the government sector in maintaining its existence and developing its organizations to achieve prime competitive advantage (As'ad, 2003: 32).

According to Morrison in Sitty Yuwalliantin (2006: 245) commitment is considered important for organization because: (1) Its influence on turnover. (2) The relationship with performance assumes that committed individuals tend to put greater effort into work. In research conducted by Benkhoff (1997: 194), organizational commitment plays an important role in improving good performance and ignoring commitment to the organization will result in losses.

Mowday and Potter in Bourantas and Papalexandris, (2003: 239) define organizational commitment as the relative strength in identifying one's involvement with the organization. They state that organizational commitment has three main components, namely: (1) Strong belief and acceptance of the organization's values and goals. (2) The desire to make hard efforts that can be accounted for on behalf of organization. (3) Strong desire to remain as a member of the organization.

Meanwhile, Allen and Meyer's study (2000: 14) differentiates organizational commitment into three components, namely: (1) Affective component of employee emotional attachment, employee identification and involvement in an organization. (2) The normative component is the employee's feelings about the obligations he must give to the organization. (3) Continuance component means a component based on the employee's perception of the losses he will face if he leaves the organization. In general, organizational commitment is considered an important measure of organizational effectiveness, Suhana (2006: 50), while according to Sulaiman (2002: 178) in his research, organizational commitment is positively related to employee performance. Bashaw and Grant (2000: 115) state that employee commitment is defined as the employee's desire to maintain their membership in the organization and are willing to make high efforts to achieve organizational goals. Furthermore, employees who are committed to the organization will show positive attitudes and behavior that tend to perform better and will remain in the organization as a form of pride in the organization, because the organization is able to meet its expectations.

B. Organizational Culture

An effective organizational culture includes good wages and rewards, communication openness, emphasis on quality, employee involvement in decision making, profit sharing for employees, fairness or equal status for employees, job security, training, freedom of opinion, emphasis on innovation, good employee-management relations, and a simple administrative structure. From various studies on organizational culture, it influences organizational aspects such as: increasing commitment organization. McKinnon et.al (2001: 37). In addition, an organization has a core culture that dominates the members of the organization as a whole. In

addition, an organization can has a strong culture in the sense of being widely, firmly and consistently embraced by its members.

Research conducted by Chen (2004: 436) shows that organizational culture and style Leadership has a significant positive effect on organizational commitment, job satisfaction and employee performance. The high support shown by company leaders is able to provide high motivation for employees to work better and achieve high performance. According to Rao (2006: 65), so that assessments to measure performance can run well, the instruments used in the assessment are required to have aspects of objectivity and fairness. To obtain an objective and fair instrument, the criteria involved in the instrument are based on key areas of achievement. This means that in each task area, the assessment criteria or benchmarks are based on the role and function. Then the performance produced by the employee related to his role and function is used as the employee's key achievement. Meanwhile, the criteria contained in DP3 are general achievements that have relatively the same level of measurement between employee roles and functions in their respective fields.

In connection with the above, measuring employee performance can be viewed from various points of view, depending on the goals of the organization itself. In general, performance measurement provides an approach to performance (achievement), but also places emphasis on efficiency values. According to Gomes (2005: 159), achievement/performance is greatly influenced by factors, namely knowledge, skills, abilities, and attitudes of workers in the organization and are a function of motivation multiplied by ability or skill.

Based on this theory, a hypothesis can be put forward, firstly, there is a partial positive and significant relationship between employee commitment and organizational culture on employee performance; secondly, there is a positive and significant relationship between commitment and organizational culture on employee performance. Thus, the aim of this research is to determine and analyze the influence of employee commitment and culture factors. Organization simultaneously (simultaneously) on the performance of the Regional Secretariat of Riau Province employees and to determine and analyze the influence of employee commitment factors and organizational culture partially on the performance of the Regional Secretariat of Riau employees.

METHODS

Based on consideration of the research objectives, this research design is a verification and quantitative descriptive analysis. The types of data required in this research are primary data and secondary data. Primary data sources were obtained from empirical research results through distributing questionnaires. Meanwhile, secondary data sources include: obtained from the annual report on the human resources profile of Riau Province, BPS, Bureau Staffing of the Governor's Office of Riau and Riau Provinces in Figures, journals, bulletins and magazines related to this research.

The population in this study were all civil servants within the Regional Secretariat (Setda) of Riau Province based on Class (Eselonering) totaling 402 people, consisting of Class I, II, III and IV employees. The sample was taken from 10% of the population using the Proportional Stratified Random Sampling sampling technique. This method is used because the population is heterogeneous and the number of employees in each stratum is not the same. The data collection technique was carried out using 1) interviews, as a direct communication technique addressed to the Regional Secretariat (Setda) of Riau Province or representing him such as Secretary, Head of Section, Head of Subdivision and Staff at the Regional Secretariat (Setda) of Riau Province; 2) Questionnaire, a list of questions made in simple form using the closed question method; and 3) Observation, observing company activities related to the problem being researched.

The method of measurement is by confronting a respondent with a question and then being asked to provide an answer; strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree, and strongly disagree. Answers are given a score of 1 to 5. To analyze the influence of organizational culture factors and employee commitment as independent variables on employee performance as a dependent variable, this research uses a multiple linear regression equation model. To determine the contribution of organizational culture and employee commitment to employee performance, the coefficient of determination is used (R^2).

Furthermore, to prove the influence of each (partial) independent variable (X_i) on the dependent variable (Y_i) in this research, each regression coefficient was tested with a t test, the results of the t test are significant if a value of $p < 0.05$ is obtained. To find out the most dominant influence from the t test results, you can see the smallest p value, this means the influence is dominant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Study Result

The results of this multiple linear regression analysis show a positive relationship between the performance factors of Riau Province Regional Secretariat (Setda) employees. Sequentially, it can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Multiple Regression

Variabel bebas	Koefisien regresi	t-test (df=37)	Prob.	Parsial r ²	Kcoef. R
Komitmen Peg. (X ₁)	0,3654	13,196	0,000	0,7874	0,870
Budaya Organisasi (X ₂)	0,1539	7,515	0,000	0,5458	0,738
Konstanta					
Signifikan dengan tingkat kepercayaan		(α) = 5 %			
Adjusted R Squared	= 0,7926	F _{hitung}	= 94,656		
R ²	= 0,801	Probabilitas	= 0,000E + 00		
Multiple R	= 0,895	F _{tabel}	= 3,195		
n	= 40	t _{tabel}	= 1,678		

Source : Processed Data

Furthermore, the results of the calculations that have been carried out show that the employee commitment variable (X1) has a positive sign with a regression coefficient of 0.3654. This positive sign means that every increase in employee commitment factors will increase the performance of Riau Province Regional Secretariat (Setda) employees if the other independent variables are constant. Theoretically, it is true that every increase in employee commitment factors will encourage increased performance.

To find out how much influence the independent variable employee commitment (X1) has on the dependent variable of Riau Province Regional Secretariat (Setda) employee performance, it can be seen in the partial coefficient of determination (r²). The partial determination coefficient of employee commitment (X1) is r² = 0.7874 or 78.74%. This means that the contribution given is a commitment-free variable employees (X1) with the dependent variable namely the performance of the Riau Province Regional Secretariat (Setda) employees is 78.74% as long as the other independent variables are constant.

Next, to see the significance level of the regression coefficient for the Employee Commitment variable, the regression coefficient is carried out using the t test. The results of the t test calculation are significant if tcount > ttable or p < 0.05. The results of the t test show that tcount of the employee commitment variable (X1) is = 13.196 with a probability of error of 0.00000 while ttable at the real level α = 0.05 is 1.678, so statistically tcount is greater than ttable or p < 0.05 . If p < 0.05 then it can be partially said that the variation in the independent variable of employee commitment is able to explain the variation in the dependent variable, namely the performance of the employees of the Regional Secretariat (Setda) of Riau Province. Thus it can be concluded that:

- a. H₀ of the Employee Commitment factor (X1) which states that the employee commitment factor partially has a significant influence not significant to the performance of Riau Province Regional Secretariat (Setda) employees, rejected.
- b. H_a from the Employee Commitment factor (X1) which states that the employee commitment factor has a significant influence on the performance of Riau Province Regional Secretariat (Setda) employees is accepted.

The results of statistical calculations show that the employee commitment variable (X1) has the most dominant influence on the performance of Regional Secretariat (Setda) officials. Riau Province. Thus, if the office environment of the Riau Regional Secretariat in particular and the regional government in general should be able to provide appropriate employee commitment, both physical and non-physical, it will be able to have a very positive influence by increasing the performance of the employees of the Riau Province Regional Secretariat (Setda). is a form of attitude and work ethic for employees that makes them able and willing to complete the work and achieve the desired goals. If the commitment you have is good then the activities carried

out will also be high, conversely if the commitment you have is small then all the activities faced will also be low.

In connection with this, in an effort to improve the performance of the Riau Province Regional Secretariat (Setda) employees, the Riau Province Regional Government should pay attention to things that are able to generate values and norms rather than employee commitment and work culture both individually and in groups.

Organizational Culture and Employee Commitment values can be grouped into; economic motives, motives to obtain opportunities to advance, motives with recognition of will self-existence, as well as self-development motives, and so on. Human needs and desires are diverse in nature, by Therefore, a leader must be able to align individual needs with organizational needs. In this way, the commitment of Riau Province Regional Secretariat (Setda) employees can be directed towards achieving common goals. In addition, to achieve this goal, a leader must be able to provide motivation from employee commitment values such as systems, mechanisms, procedures, norms from the existing organizational culture to his employees that can fulfill the hopes and desires of the Provincial Regional Secretariat (Setda) employees. Riau.

The fairly strong positive relationship and influence between the independent variables (employee commitment and organizational culture) simultaneously and the performance of the Riau Province Regional Secretariat (Setda) employees is shown by the magnitude of the coefficient of determination (R^2) which is 0.8011, which shows that the independent variable varies simultaneously has a significant influence on variations in the dependent variable, namely the performance of the Riau Province Regional Secretariat (Setda) employees at 80.11% while the remaining 19.89% illustrates the magnitude of the dependent variable influenced by other independent variables that were not observed in this research.

This condition illustrates that the higher employee commitment and organizational culture of Riau Province Regional Secretariat employees will further improve performance, including in providing services to the community. An effective organizational culture includes good wages and rewards, open communication, emphasis on quality, employee involvement in decision making, profit sharing for employees, fairness or equal status for employees, job security, training, freedom of opinion, emphasis on innovation, relationships. good employees and management, and a simple administrative structure.

This is also in line with the opinion of Reilly, et. al (1999: 173), that commitment is closely related between a person's mental condition and his organization, which includes a sense of involvement in work, loyalty and belief in the values of the organization. In addition, employee commitment to the organization is an attitude taken by employees, however, it will determine their behavior as a manifestation of that attitude individual. Behavioral consequences that emerge as a manifestation of high levels of employee commitment to the organization include low levels of employee turnover, low levels of absenteeism, high work ethic and motivation, liking work that is responsible and trying to achieve high work performance. On the other hand, employee commitment is a condition where organizational members provide their abilities and loyalty to the organization in achieving its goals in return for the satisfaction they obtain (Hodge, et.al, 2003: 22).

Achieving the goals of an organization is only possible because of the efforts of the actors in the organization. Therefore, building commitment is necessary a powerful trigger as the results of previous research by Odom, et al (2001: 167) stated that there is a positive relationship between organizational culture and employee commitment. In this view, culture is considered as a trigger for the growth of employee commitment because the culture that is built is in line with the values held by employees. Employees who accept the core values of organizational culture will show an attitude of commitment to the organization. Employees easily absorb and understand the values and norms adopted by the organization and apply these values and norms in the work environment as guidelines for behavior. Furthermore, employees who are committed to the organization will show positive attitudes and behavior that tend to perform better and will remain in the organization as a form of pride in the organization, because the organization is able to meet its expectations.

In assessing an employee's performance, the most dominant element is the source human resources, because even though the planning has been prepared neatly and well, if the employees or personnel who are reflected in carrying out their work in a particular organizational structure are not enthusiastic or passionate in the sense of a lack of motivation given, then the planning will be in vain, therefore some companies consider it a problem employee coaching or development is very important, so they set up training or development centers. In addition, efforts to build commitment are described as efforts to establish long-term relationships. Individuals who are committed to the organization are more likely to remain in the organization than individuals who are not committed. They tend to show high involvement which is manifested in the form of attitudes and behavior.

Thus, employee commitment will emerge if they understand work culture values, communicate performance standards and link them to rewards, take effective evaluation actions and provide support to supervisors and leaders. The results of research conducted by Robinson, et al (1999: 17) state that one of the predictors of commitment is the perception of organizational culture which is linked to employee performance, where this commitment will lead to three measures of organizational outcomes, namely job satisfaction, motivation and work performance. . Individual achievement will be achieved well if it is supported by a set of conducive norms that regulate individual behavior regarding what can be done and what cannot be done, how to interact with others, thus culture influences employee behavior on how to act in their environment.

A culture that is firmly embedded in the organization, where cultural values are well accepted and employees implement them in accordance with established norms, will reveal the extent to which employees can achieve. The relationship between how employees perceive organizational culture and performance will become increasingly apparent in the quality of employee work, whether it increases or decreases. According to Goodman, et al (2001: 163) describe how a strong culture can help employees do their jobs better, because organizational culture provides a perspective or perception for employees to understand the expected behavior. A high sense of employee commitment and performance towards the organization will have a positive impact on achievement employee work in the organization.

Furthermore, according to Schein (2001: 138) states that organizational culture is important becomes very important for the survival of the organization, especially when connected with the organization's efforts to overcome various problems in adapting to various external developments and changes and integrating internal forces. Culture can have a significant influence on the attitudes and behavior of organizational members. Strong cultures also often help business performance because they create unusual levels of motivation. Sometimes these feelings make employees share their values and behavior and make them feel comfortable or compatible with the work environment in the organization, feel committed or loyal and make people work harder, and see work as something interesting.

High commitment according to Somers and Mark John (2005: 147) is demonstrated by, among other things, low levels of employee turnover, low levels of absenteeism, high work motivation, satisfaction with what has been done and striving to achieve high performance. These opinions show that the work commitment of employees within the Regional Secretariat of Riau Province should be demonstrated by their work motivation height that arises from within the employee, not due to external stimulation. So this situation must be taken seriously by the regional government, so that the work commitment that exists among employees is not a commitment due to compulsion, but truly arises from within the employees themselves. This kind of commitment will bring high employee loyalty to the work unit organization.

In order to improve the organizational culture of employees within the Regional Secretariat of Riau Province, namely increasing friendliness. Improvement can be done by cultivating a friendly culture towards various parties (community or other work units). The less friendly impression of civil servants in general and employees within the Regional Secretariat of Riau Province shows that friendliness needs to be improved. This can be done by bringing in consultants in the field of excellent service from the parties private sector that has proven credibility and experience. So that the negative, arrogant and unfriendly impression of employees can be removed to become a positive, friendly and friendly impression of employees. Apart from that, the strategic impact of organizational commitment on employee performance is to foster a sense of pride in being part of the organization.

Leaders must be able to build employees' personal pride in belonging organization by ensuring that civil servants are servants of the state and society, and are grateful for having become civil servants, while many other people want to join. Therefore, for the regional government of Riau province, human resources are the main asset that is the foundation of hope for the survival, progress and development of government organizations in the future. For this reason, human resource development is always sought along with the progress and development of organizations, market competition and commitment to providing the best to civil society.

CONCLUSION

This research concludes that based on the analysis of statistical test calculations that have been carried out discussed by the author shows that the factors of employee commitment and organizational culture simultaneously (overall test) have a very significant influence on the performance of employees of the Regional

Secretariat (Setda) of Riau Province. Likewise, employee commitment and organizational culture, which have a partial and significant influence on the performance of employees of the Riau Province Regional Secretariat (Setda), can be declared to be true.

However, even though the performance of the Riau Province Regional Secretariat (Setda) employees is the average is in the high category, however, management and all office leaders must pay attention to policies directed at employees who are truly loyal in completing and achieving work quality standards desired by the regional government by digging up information from each employee from various parties and related agencies regarding the factors causing their low performance.

Organizational culture factors have a dominant influence on the performance of Riau Province Regional Secretariat (Setda) employees. Therefore, it would be best for the office, executive leaders and staff to pay greater attention to the demands of employee welfare levels, such as the need to prepare facilities and work infrastructure to carry out daily work in the field in order to achieve the quality of work standards that have been determined, in addition to human resource career development, self-recognition and rules and procedures for benefit programs provided by the government to its employees. Incentive program activities in order to provide commitment to work will be effective and efficient if the concepts, mechanisms, rules and procedures as well as work program materials can be understood and attract employees in carrying out their work.

Therefore, it is best for employees to be equipped with increased abilities and skills in accordance with their respective fields of work. For this reason, this needs to be done training for trainers activities for employees who are truly committed and consistent in carrying out their daily duties. This research examines the influence of two independent variables consisting of employee commitment factors and organizational culture on the performance of Riau Province Regional Secretariat (Setda) employees. In connection with this, there are many other variables that can be studied by other researchers for the purposes of developing knowledge in the field of human resource management, including motivation which can help organizational leaders to increase employee commitment to the organization.

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